

PHRASEOLOGY IS AS AN IMPORTANT DEPARTMENT OF LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: The article is devoted to an overview of phraseology, presenting phraseological units in German and Uzbek linguists' classifications. They are given general conclusions by analyzing the views of linguists.

Keywords: phrase, phraseology, lexeme, morpheme, syntactic connection, linguistic unit

Аннотация: Статья посвящена обзору фразеологизмов, представлению фразеологических единиц в классификациях немецких и узбекских лингвистов. В ходе исследования были выявлены общие выводы на основе анализа взглядов лингвистов.

Ключевые слова: словосочетание, фразеология, лексема, морфема, синтаксическая связь, языковая единица.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada nemis va o'zbek tilshunoslari tasnifidagi frazeologik birliklar taqdim etilgan holda frazeologiyaga umumiy nuqtai nazar bag'ishlangan. Tilshunos olimlarning fikrlarini tahlil qilib, ularga umumiy xulosalar beriladi.

Tayanch so'zlar: fraza, frazeologizm, leksema, morfema, sintaktik bog`lanish, lisoniy birlik.

Introduction: As a branch of linguistics, the subject of phraseology is the study of categorical signs of phraseological units, based on which the main signs of phraseological units are determined and the issue of the essence of phraseological units as special units of the language is resolved. as well as to

determine the laws of phraseological units in speech and the processes of their formation. However, when there is one research topic and a lot of phraseology despite the fact that questions have been developed in detail, there are still different points of view about what a phraseological unit is, as in the volume of phraseology of the Russian language. The list of phraseological units of the Russian language proposed by different scholars is so different from each other that for some reason we can talk about different, often contradictory, even mutually exclusive views on the research topic. The scientific terminology used to define the corresponding concepts... This explains the ambiguity of the understanding of the tasks, purposes, and essence of the term "phraseology" and the lack of a clear enough single classification of phraseological turns in the Russian language in terms of semantic unification. However, the most common (with clarifications and additions) is the classification of V. V. Vinogradov. Therefore, finally, many things in the Russian phraseological system have just begun to be studied.

Research: In linguistics, there are various opportunities for vocabulary enrichment. The vocabulary of the language consists mainly of words. By lexical units, we understand not only individual words but also fixed word combinations (phrases, fixed phrases, phraseological units). Phraseology (Greek phrases - expression, phrase, and ...logy) - 1) a branch of linguistics that examines the phraseological structure of the language in its current state and historical development; 2) a set of phraseologies in a particular language. "For a broader definition of phraseology, it is necessary to pay attention to its theoretical and practical aspects. Phraseology is the phraseology of language phenomena today it is the cause of various debates.

The main focus of phraseology as a branch of linguistics is to study the nature of phraseology and its categorical features, as well as to determine the laws of the use of phraseology in speech.

The most important problem of phraseology is to differentiate and distinguish phraseologies from word combinations that are formed in speech (that is, not ready in advance) and on this basis to determine the signs of phraseologies. Based on certain differences between idiomatic phraseology, phraseological combinations and stable sentences (proverbs and proverbs, other phraseological equivalents), many researchers understand phraseology in 2 ways: narrow and broad. It is in a broad sense when understood, that proverbs and proverbs, characteristic of folklore, belong to the circle of phraseology sentences, some forms of communication (greetings, farewell sentences) are also included. But this issue, that is, the issue of understanding phraseology in a broad sense, is still controversial. The main tasks or issues of phraseology: determining the consistency of phraseological content and, in this regard, studying the sign(s) of phraseology; description of homonymy, synonymy, antonymy, polysemy and variation of phraseology; determining the specific features of the words used in phraseology and their specific meanings; clarifying the relationship between phraseology and word groups; determine their syntactic role; study of formation of new meanings of words within phraseological units and other phraseology develops principles of separation of phraseological units, methods of their study, classification and description in dictionaries. On the basis of unique, diverse methods developed in phraseology, the phraseological composition of the language is classified according to different: structural-semantic, grammatical, task-methodical bases. The principle of structural-semantic classification is the main one.

Analysis: Phraseology as an independent branch of linguistics appeared in Russian linguistics in the 40s of the 20th century. Its initial formation was based on the works of Russian scientists A.A. Potebnya, I.I. Sreznevsky, A. A. Shakhmatov, while the issue of studying stable (stable) word combinations in a separate department of linguistics - phraseology - in the educational and

methodological literature of the 20s-40s - Ye. D. Polivanov, S. Abakumov, mentioned in the works of L.A. Bulakhovsky. In Western European and American linguistics, phraseology is not distinguished as a separate branch of linguistics. Before analyzing these word combinations in depth, let's focus on the concept of word combinations. "Words do not usually exist in a language separately, but in the form of a free syntactic combination. Free syntactic combinations are grammatical combinations of two or more words. Such syntactic phrases can be analyzed from a semantic point of view. Because each component of such a word combination can have its original meaning and figurative meaning. The general meaning of all word combinations arises from the combination of the meanings of their components"³. The point of view of the science of phraseology is ambiguous, the first meaning of which is all fixed phrases (phraseologies) with a figurative meaning. generalization and the second meaning refers to a branch of linguistics that studies stable word combinations. Many linguists are dealing with various problems of phraseology. Many scientific works in English are devoted to actual problems of phraseology. There you can find a detailed understanding of the meanings of phraseology and a lot of important information about their origin. But there are no theoretical explanations of phraseologies. These works have specific features that can be used for background information.

In the current period of the development of the science of linguistics, the study of the problems inherent in phraseological units remains one of the most urgent issues on the agenda. If we look at the history of the language, the problems related to phraseology have been constantly the focus of attention of linguists.

The history of the study of phraseology covers two centuries. The systematic study of phraseologies in Uzbek linguistics began in the works of Sh. Rakhmatullayev, Ya. Pinkhasov, A. Shomaqsudov, M. Husainov. "It should be noted that in the scientific literature, this language unit is called phraseology,

phraseological unit, and it is better to call it phraseme, analogous to the terms lexeme and morpheme. A phraseme as a linguistic unit is equivalent to a symbol in the language memory of the brain: when using a phraseme, it is this symbol that is copied.

As a linguistic unit, a phrase is equal to a part, it becomes a whole only after the addition of certain grammatical features and is used in speech. Phraseologies as a linguistic unit consists of a unity of two aspects - the aspect of expression and the aspect of content. The expressive aspect of phraseologies is understood as the language units they originally consist of. Phraseology occurs when two or more lexemes are semantically-syntactically connected and discover a generalized figurative meaning. In phraseologies, a certain pattern of a combination, sentence form is filled with lexemes and morphemes as a permanent component.

Conclusion: In conclusion, we can say that not only the lexemes in its composition belong to the expressive aspect of the phrase, but also the morphemes that participate as a permanent component of the phrase, because such morphemes, and the adjective, also belong to the internal grammatical structure of the phrase. Only the morphemes that are added in connection with the use of a phrase in speech do not belong to its expressive aspect.

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